

Tungro infection in IR varieties, IRRI farm, April 1981.

varieties and TN1 as the susceptible check were transplanted in 2.2- × 1.2-m field plots at 20- × 20-cm spacing. A

row of tungro-infected TN1 seedlings planted around each plot served as a source of infection.

One week after transplanting, 100 *N. virescens* adults were caged on tungro-infected TN1 plants at the center of each plot. The insects were released 24 hours after caging. Treatments were replicated three times. Sixty days after release of the hoppers, tungro-infected hills were counted, and tungro infection was computed for each plot.

IR28, IR29, IR30, IR34, IR40, IR50, IR52, and IR54 had low levels of tungro infection (see figure). In general, varieties most resistant in the SBT also had the lowest tungro infection. In the IR varieties the degree of tungro infection in the field apparently is related to the degree of *N. virescens* resistance indicated by the SBT. ■

Response to insecticides of green leafhoppers from four sites in the Philippines

L. Fabellar, E. A. Heinrichs, and H. Rapugas, The International Rice Research Institute

To measure the development of insecticide resistance in green leafhoppers *Nephotettix virescens*, cultures collected from four sites in the Philippines were compared with a greenhouse culture. The insects originated from Pangasinan, Nueva Ecija, and Tarlac Provinces in Central Luzon.

Insecticide solutions of acephate, methyl parathion, MIPC, and monocrotophos were prepared. Three- to seven-day-old adult insects were anaesthetized and sprayed with 2 ml of the insecticide solution at rates of 0.125, 0.25, 0.4, 0.5, and 0.75 kg a.i./ha with a Potter's spray tower. Each treatment of 25 insects was replicated twice.

Treated insects were transferred to potted 2-week-old rice seedlings, covered with mylar cages (15.38 cm tall, 3.50 cm in diameter), and placed in 25° C to 27° C temperature, 60 to 80% relative humidity and 12 hours light. Mortality was recorded 48 hours after treatment and the computed lethal concentrations to kill 50% of the population (LC₅₀) were compared between colonies (see table).

Cultures from Palayan had 1.32-fold resistance to acephate and 2.02-fold re-

Resistance of field-collected green leafhoppers to insecticides (LC₅₀^a values). IRRI insectary, 1980.

Source of culture (Philippines)	Level of resistance ^b			
	Acephate	Methyl parathion ^c	MIPC	Monocrotophos
Palayan, Nueva Ecija	1.32 ^d	2.02 ^d	0.86	0.84
Santa Maria, Pangasinan	1.36 ^d	1.11	0.28	0.62
Rosales, Pangasinan	0.95	1.12	0.28	0.53
Pura, Tarlac	1.00	1.24	0.52	0.53

^aLC₅₀ = lethal concentration in kg a.i./ha applied in Potter's spray tower to kill 50% of the insect population. ^bLevel of resistance = $\frac{LC_{50} \text{ of field-collected culture}}{LC_{50} \text{ of greenhouse culture}}$. Resistance ratio of >1.0 indicates field culture resistance greater than greenhouse culture. ^cPENNCAP M formulation. ^dCultures with significantly higher (5% level) LC₅₀ values than the greenhouse culture.

sistance to methyl parathion. Cultures from Santa Maria had 1.36-fold resistance to acephate.

Methyl parathion and monocrotophos are probably the insecticides most

commonly used in the Philippines. The low level of resistance to the four insecticides indicates that resistance would not be a problem for farmers at the four sites. ■

Resistance of rice varieties to the green leafhopper in Southern India

S. Chelliah and A. M. Hanifa, Tamil Nadu Agricultural University, Coimbatore, India; and E. A. Heinrichs and G. S. Khush, International Rice Research Institute

Resistance of rice varieties to the green leafhopper (GLH) *Nephotettix virescens* (Distant) was studied in an international collaborative research project. Eleven varieties with known resistance genes, four varieties with unknown resistance genes, and resistant and susceptible checks were screened.

Test varieties were planted in seedboxes (60 × 40 × 10 cm) in 15 cm rows, replicated three times. Seedlings were

thinned to 30/ row 7 days after sowing. Seedboxes were infested with GLH adults (about 2/seedling), covered with nylon mesh cages, and maintained on galvanized on trays containing 6 cm water.

Damage rating began 6 days after infestation (DI) and continued to 11 DI. The 1-9 damage rating scale of the Standard Evaluation System for Rice was used. The rating at 9 DI, when 2 test varieties scored 8, was used to judge GLH resistance.

Moddai Karuppan with gene *Glh 7*, Ptb 8 with *glh 4*, and TAPL 796 with *Glh 6* had the highest levels of resistance (see table). ASD7 (*Glh 2*), IR8 (*Glh 3*), and ASD8 (*Glh 5*) were moderately resistant. Pankhari 203 (*Glh 1*) was

Green leafhopper (*Nephotettix virescens* Dist.) resistance ratings of rice varieties with different resistance genes, Coimbatore, India.

Variety	Resistance gene ^a	Damage rating ^b					
		6 DI	7 DI	8 DI	9 DI	10 DI	11 DI
Pankhari 203	<i>Glh 1</i>	9.0 c	9.0 d	9.0 e	9.0 e	9.0 d	9.0 d
ASD 7	<i>Glh 2</i>	2.3 a	3.0 ab	5.0 bcd	5.7 cde	7.0 cd	7.7 d
IR8	<i>Glh 3</i>	1.7 a	3.7 b	5.0 bcd	6.3 de	7.0 cd	1.0 cd
Ptb 8	<i>glh 4</i>	1.0 a	2.3 ab	2.3 abc	3.0 abc	3.7 ab	3.1 ab
ASD 8	<i>Glh 5</i>	1.0 a	3.0 ab	3.7 abcd	5.0 bcd	5.7 bc	7.0 d
TAPL 196	<i>Glh 6</i>	1.7 a	1.7 ab	3.0 abcd	3.7 abcd	3.7 ab	5.0 bc
Moddai Karuppan	<i>Glh 7</i>	1.0 a	1.0 a	1.0 a	1.0 a	1.7 a	2.3 a
IR20	<i>Glh 3</i>	1.7 a	3.7 b	5.7 cde	6.3 de	7.7 cd	7.7 d
IR24	NA	2.3 a	3.7 b	5.7 cde	7.0 de	7.7 cd	7.7 d
IR26	NA	1.0 a	1.0 a	1.7 ab	2.3 ab	3.0 a	3.0 ab
IR36	<i>Glh 6</i>	1.7 a	1.7 ab	1.7 ab	1.7 ab	1.7 a	1.7 a
IR42	NA	1.7 a	1.7 ab	2.3 abc	3.0 abc	3.0 a	3.0 ab
IR50	NA	1.0 a	1.7 ab	1.7 ab	1.7 ab	1.7 a	1.7 a
IR54	NA	1.7 a	1.7 ab	3.0 abcd	2.3 ab	2.3 a	2.3 a
IR29 (resistant check)	NA	1.0 a	1.7 ab	1.7 ab	1.7 ab	2.3 a	3.0 ab
TN1 (susceptible check)	-	5.0 b	6.3 c	7.0 de	8.3 e	8.3 d	9.0 d

^aNA = not ascertained. ^bScored by the Standard Evaluation System for Rice. Within a column, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level. DI = days after infestation.

susceptible.

Genes *Glh 1*, *Glh 2*, *Glh 3*, *glh 4*, and *Glh 5* were identified at IRRI using a Philippine population of *N. virescens*

Genes *Glh 6* and *Glh 7* were identified in Bangladesh.

Pankhari 203, which is susceptible at Coimbatore, is highly resistant in the

Philippines. On the other hand, Moddai Karuppan is moderately susceptible in the Philippines but is highly resistant at Coimbatore and Bangladesh. ■

Resistance of rice cultivars and wild rices to thrips

R. Velusamy, S. Chelliah, and J. Chandramohan, Tamil Nadu Agricultural University, Coimbatore-641003, India

Among yield nursery seedlings of rice cultivars and wild rices screened for thrips *Baliothrips biformis* (Bagnall) resistance, Ptb 33, BG379-1, and Kalubalawee Sudurvi 305 were highly resistant. Gangala, Utri Rajappan, BG367-1, BG367-9, BG379-5, OB678, and IR17494-32-1-1-3-2 were resistant.

Wild rices found resistant to thrips at Coimbatore, India.

IRRI accession number	Name	Origin	Rating
103437	<i>O. glaberrima</i>	Senegal	1
103443	<i>O. glaberrima</i>	Senegal	1
103831	<i>O. sariva</i> f. <i>spontanea</i>	Bangladesh	1
103836	<i>O. nivara</i>	Bangladesh	1
101171	<i>O. eichingeri</i>	Tanzania	3
101510	<i>O. nivara</i>	India	3
101993	<i>O. rufipogon</i> / <i>O. nivara</i>	Sri Lanka	3
103438	<i>O. glaberrima</i>	Senegal	3
103791	<i>O. nivara</i> / <i>O. sativa</i>	Venezuela	3
103826	<i>O. sativa</i> f. <i>spontanea</i>	Bangladesh	3
103849	<i>O. perennis</i>	India	3

Eleven wild rices were resistant (see table). Varieties BG367-1, BG367-9, BG379-1, BG379-5, IR17494-32-1-1-3-2, and OB678 also were resistant to brown planthopper. ■

Reaction of gall midge-resistant cultures at Warangal, India

V. L. V. Prasada Rao, N. Venugopal Rao, and P. Satyanarayana Reddy, Agricultural Research Station, Warangal 506 007, India

The Agricultural Research Station, Warangal, India, collaborated with the All India Cooperative Rice Improvement Project and IRRI in a study to identify gall midge biotypes and their distribution in India.

Field screening was conducted from 1977 to 1980. Observations on midge incidence were made on hill and tiller

Call midge biotype collaborative study, Warangal, India, and IRRI, 1978-80.

Culture	Hills infested (%)			Reaction ^a
	1978	1979	1980	
<i>Leuang 152</i>				
Leuang 152	0	0	0	R
CR95-JR-46-1	0	0	0	R
CR95-JR-214	0	14	0	MR
<i>Ptb</i>				
Ptb 10	0	— ^b	—	R
Ptb 18	0	0	4	R
Ptb 21	0	0	4	R
CR157-392-4	4	0	—	R
CR94-13	5	4	—	R
IR36	0	2	22	S
<i>Eswarakora</i>				
W1263	0	0	2	R
Kakatiya	0	0	0	R

(Continued on next page)